

Calming visual spaces
Learning from Kyoto Zen gardens

Michael J. Lyons, Gert J. Van Tonder
Ian Shortreed, Nobuji Tetsutani

ATR Media Information Science Labs
Kyoto University (GJVT)

Aesthetic qualities of Zen gardens

Karesansui - dry landscape gardens

Muromachi era (1336 - 1573)

- naturalness
- asymmetry
- simplicity
- tranquility

Shinichi Hisamatsu

scene elements → aesthetic qualities

Natural textures

Hypothesis

Zen gardens are visually calm because they:

- simplify task of scene understanding
- minimize visual pop-out
- reduce load on attentional resources

Scene perception

Scene segmentation

Gestalt principles

proximity

✘ This image cannot currently be displayed.

✘ This image cannot currently be displayed.

similarity

continuity

✘ This image cannot currently be displayed.

✘ This image cannot currently be displayed.

closure

Gestalt principles

Simplicity

Complex interaction of cues

Contour junctions

Junction type
odd even

Object arrangement

Aligned even junctions
cause competing figures

An observation

- gestalt principles seem to be used to ease segmentation of visually salient objects such as paths, bridges, or buildings
- “pop-out” is scrupulously avoided in other areas of the garden or in object parts
- The garden designers seem to have understood visual Gestalt very well!

Scene segmentation

Scene perception

Perceptual Grouping

Perceptual Grouping

Multiscale grouping

Multiscale grouping

Zuihouin - Dokuzatei garden

“garden of solitary meditation”

Zuihouin - baroque version

Ryoanji dry landscape garden

yohaku no bi - the beauty of empty space

Landscape painting

Fan Kuan
990-1030, Sung

Mi Fei
1051-1107, Sung

Sesshu
1495, Muromachi

To members of the Press

- The following material is in the process of publication by a journal which has a "press embargo" policy
- *Please contact me* before reporting the following material

mlyons@atr.co.jp

Medial axis transform

- Proposed by H. Blum in 60's as a natural representation for computer vision
- Kovacs, Julesz et al. found axes of enhanced luminance contrast perception at MAT maxima

Ryoanji: Symmetry axes

Medial axes in
the 1681 plan

Medial axes in
the present plan

Scale space analysis

Simulated design alterations

Ryoanji: an interpretation

- Implicit structure of visual ground may account for this garden's appeal
- Patterned visual ground lends "wholeness" to the composition

Summary

- Consideration of perceptual processes in early vision can yield insight into affect-level qualities of visual environments
- Gestalt principles can be helpful in this respect
- The medial axis transform is useful for exploring the structure of both visual figure and visual ground (or "empty space")

Conclusion

- This work is preliminary but it appears that vision science can help to deepen insight into Japanese dry landscape gardens
- It may be possible for designers to apply this insight in other realms to create visually calm and healing environments